

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

D6.1 Governance set-up proceedings

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Change History

Version Number	Date	Status	Name	Summary of Main Changes
1	23/09/2022	DRAFT	Initial Draft	
2	26/09/2022	FINAL	Final text, sent to BoD and SCC	Minor changes
3	30/09/2022	FINAL	Final text, approved by BoD	Minor changes

Author(s)

Name	Beneficiary	Role
Francesca Cadeddu	FSCIRE	WP Leader

Distribution List

Name	Beneficiary	Role
BoD, SCC		

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1 Setting-up the governance

RESILIENCE PPP members met in Bologna on June, 23-24, 2022 for the project's kick-off meeting.

Among the objectives of the meeting, one was to establish and populate the governance of the project.

The general governance of the RI is described in detail in D8.1, RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and Management and Access Policy, resulted from the RESILIENCE project (Grant Agreement no. 871127). Section 2.8 of the document describes the specific Interim governance for the Preparatory Phase of the RI, which is adopted and adapted by RESILIENCE PPP.

Interim Governance Bodies are:

- **General Assembly**, which is composed of representatives of the partners of the consortium. It is the ultimate decision-making body deciding on strategic issues such as membership and the overall budget.
- **Interim Council**, which is a non-executive body composed of the representatives of the national ministries of partners involved in RESILIENCE. It advises RESILIENCE with regard to the ERIC application process. The Interim Council, established at this early stage, serves as a forum in which the ministries can discuss the processes involved in the ERIC application and the relevant documents prepared by the consortium in order to facilitate the establishment of the ERIC. It serves also as a blueprint for the establishment of the later ERIC Assembly.
- **Interim Directors**, whose Board consists of the General Executive Director and two Deputy Directors. It is responsible for further refining statutes, policies and strategies, oversees the implementation of the agreed-upon work plan through Units and may initiate ad-hoc working groups.
- **Support Office**, located at the headquarters in Bologna, Italy, which includes an accountant, a secretary, and a communications officer coordinating and executing the public relations of the RI.
- **Units**, which are installed in order to develop the services of the RI, are operated by staff contributed by the partners, are linked to the planned contributions and in line with the service clusters defined by the consortium (cf. *Infra*).
- **Service Coordination Committee**, composed by the chairs of the Units, which coordinates and harmonises the work in the Units and represents the Units towards other governance bodies. The Units' chairs conduct regular meetings and oversee the implementation of the agreed-upon tasks.

A DESCA Agreement will soon be signed by all beneficiaries, also describing the rules of the governing bodies of the RESILIENCE PPP.

2 RESILIENCE PPP bodies and people

The **General Assembly (GenA)** members are:

- Alberto Melloni, FSCIRE
- Yaakov Mascetti, BIU
- Antonella Guidazzoli, CINECA
- Denis Pelletier, EPHE
- Marco Büchler, INFAl
- Dries Bosschaert, KU Leuven
- Anna-Maria Totomanova, UNISOFIA
- Herman Selderhuis, TUA
- Genta Rexha, UFO
- Ahmet Alibašić, UNSA
- Michał Choptiany, UNIWARSAW
- Nikolaos Asproulis, VOLOS
- Hans-Peter Grosshans, WWU MÜNSTER

During its first meeting online on Tuesday, February 1st, 2022, the GenA:

- 1) Elected the Interim Board of Directors, composed by Francesca Cadeddu (FSCIRE) as Executive Director, Ahmet Alibasic (UNSA) and Roxanne Wyns (KU Leuven) as Deputy Directors;
- 2) Elected its Chair, Alberto Melloni (FSCIRE), and Deputy Chairs, Anna-Maria Totomanova (UNISOFIA) and Yaakov-Akiva Mascetti (BIU);
- 3) Established two GenA sub-committees to closely follow strategic aspects of the infrastructure, such as the enlargement procedures and the composition of the Advisory Board.
 - **Enlargement sub-committee:** Herman Selderhuis (Chair, TUA), Hans-Peter Grosshans (WWU Muenster)
 - **Advisory Board sub-committee:** Hans-Peter Grosshans (Chair, WWU Muenster), Herman Selderhuis (TUA), Michał Choptiany (UNIWARSAW)

Members of the Committees may be joined by other GenA members in the future.

The **Interim Board of Directors (BoD)** met for the first time on February 24th, 2022. Concerning the governance of the RI:

- 1) Directors agreed to have Karla Boersma (TUA) as a permanent participant in the BoD meetings as she is the supervisor and coordinator of the RESILIENCE communication strategy, both internal and external;
- 2) Francesca Cadeddu presented the Support office, composed of Irene Iarocci in the role of Secretary and Maria Parrella in the role of Accountant. An expert in communication will be hired starting from January 2023.
- 3) With the purpose of matching the RESILIENCE PPP with the governance envisioned in the above-mentioned D8.1, RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and Management and Access Policy, Directors revised some structural aspects (i.e., Units are now called Working Units (WU); RESILIENCE PPP Work Package (WP) 5 on Impact is absorbed in WP3 as a dedicated WU) and agreed on the following structure:

Work Package	Lead Beneficiary	Working Unit
Sustainability	FSCIRE	<i>HR and Other Resources</i>
		<i>Funding</i>
Services	KU Leuven	<i>Data</i>
		<i>IT</i>
		<i>TNA</i>
Users	WWU Münster	<i>User Requirements</i>
		<i>Impact</i>
Communication	TUA	<i>Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation</i>
		<i>Training</i>
Project Management	FSCIRE	

WP leaders and WU leaders have been subsequently indicated by the Lead Beneficiaries as follows:

Work Package	WP Leader	Working Unit	WU Leader
Sustainability	Francesca Cadeddu, FSCIRE	<i>HR and Other Resources</i>	Maria Parrella, FSCIRE
		<i>Funding</i>	Herman Selderhuis, TUA
Services	Dries Bosschaert, KU Leuven	<i>Data</i>	Michiel De Clerk, KU Leuven
		<i>IT</i>	Rudy Demo, FSCIRE
		<i>TNA</i>	Lieneke Timpers, KU Leuven
Users	Hans-Peter Grosshans, WWU Muenster	<i>User Requirements</i>	Lena Mausbach and Daniel Scheuermann, WWU Münster
		<i>Impact</i>	Emir Vajzovic, UNSA
Communication	Karla Boersma, TUA	<i>Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation</i>	Karla Boersma, TUA
		<i>Training</i>	Herman Selderhuis, TUA
Project Management	Francesca Cadeddu, FSCIRE		

The Service Coordination Committee, composed by all WU Leaders and the BoD, met for the first time in Palermo on August 29-31st, 2022. By September 15th, 2022 all WU have been populated by the beneficiaries in the RESILIENCE PPP directory, for private use only.

3 Meetings: typology and frequency

During the kick-off meeting it was agreed to fix the following meetings (frequency in parenthesis):

- 1) Effort/funds monitoring (every 6 months, convened by Maria Parrella, FSCIRE)
- 2) Communication monitoring (quarterly, convened by Karla Boersma, TUA)
- 7) BoD meetings (at least twice a year, preferably bi-monthly, convened by Directors)
- 8) Service Coordination Committee (monthly, on the first Wednesday of each month, at 10am, convened by Francesca Cadeddu , FSCIRE)
- 9) Meetings of the GenA (at least twice a year) will be determined from time to time.
- 10) Annual conferences and other events are a matter of further discussion in the BoD

A RESILIENCE calendar is made available on the project management online tool.

4 Applicable Documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

ID	Date	Title/Reference

5 Reference Documents

Reference documents are intended to provide background and supplementary information.

ID	Date	Title/Reference
1		RESILIENCE Governance, HR Policy and Management and Access Policy, resulted from the RESILIENCE project (Grant Agreement no. 871127)
2		RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase. First BoD Meeting, 24/02/2022 – Minutes
3		RESILIENCE Preparatory Phase. First General Assembly, 01/02/2022 – Minutes
4		RESILIENCE PPP, KICK OFF MEETING, Bologna, June 23-24, 2022 (presentation by CAF)

6 Revision Log

ID	Date	Nature of Revision	Approved by
1	30/09/2022	Final approval before upload on EC webportal	BoD

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